

Impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on Modern Businesses

Shavkatxodjayev Rasulxo'ja

Student of Millat Umidi University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Article information:

Manuscript received: 09 Oct 2024; **Accepted:** 10 Nov 2024; **Published:** 11 Dec 2024

Abstract: AI is transforming organizational contexts of contemporary businesses by opening a range of new prospects for organizational learning, performance enhancement, and product or service innovation. This article explores the transformative impact of AI across key areas: managerial, competitive advantage, insight on client satisfaction, new opportunities and business use, and overall market uptake. Education which automated with the help of AI, has made ways easier, cheap, and more accurate in the manufacturing and delivery business. The data analytics feature helps the businesses make smart strategic plans while a customer is more likely to engage with a brand that is creating a custom-tailored customer experience.

Some of the specific suggestions I made for the businesses in this article were to investment in talent and training, ethical practices, strategic AI integration and last one is continuous evaluation for incorporation into business processes. Through recognising and responding to AI issues that organizations face and with use of AI benefits, the later is viable in handling the current key issues in digital age strategic development.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, AI in Business, Operational Efficiency, Data-Driven Decision Making, Customer Personalization, Emerging Opportunities, AI Adoption Trends, AI Integration, Business Innovation.

1. Introduction

Artificial intelligence is gaining breakthrough status in today's business world as it offers new methods and tools for the development of organisational practices of companies. This indicates that industries around the world have started to incorporate artificial intelligence technologies into their operations, and in this context, we can say that it is not just a novelty they are trying to make money on, but it can rightly be called one of the components of digitalisation. It goes without saying that industries depend on industries such as the automation of complex processes and sophisticated data analysis, without which it is impossible to exist in the present and future and an ever more complex and dynamically changing market environment. But the AI adoption journey is fraught with challenges - from how to allocate resources to an AI project to how to integrate liberal AI policies into commercial objectives.

For example, industries such as retail, healthcare, finance, manufacturing and virtually all others are embedding AI into their business processes in an effort to improve business efficiency, optimise customer service and create a better and more efficient supply chain. That is, chatbots and voice assistants are creating a new form of modern customer relationships, and on the other hand, predictive analytics allows an organisation to anticipate market developments. However, there are organisations that are not responding well to AI challenges because as the number of AI challenges at the company level increases, especially as AI is incorporated into the corporate business structure within existing business architectures.

Thus, AI can be promising, but it should be used from an organisation's perspective as a technology for change and development that needs first-class leadership. For AI to be truly effective, business organizations must: have a good AI strategy, create and invest in a robust architecture for AI, and implement continuous learning for AI. Given the current progress of learning algorithms and the complete rationalization of AI technologies, the future of the advanced commercial world will be determined by how effectively or ineffectively AI functions are implemented to shape change in the marketplace.

Research shows that businesses that are purposeful about AI and incorporate it into their vision or mission are likely to benefit by differentiating themselves in the digital economy. But, as we learn in this article, the roadmap to effectively applying AI is full of challenges, and anyone working in this field needs to be aware of both the technical aspects of AI and the commercial world.

2. Literature review

Business leaders have long cited artificial intelligence (AI) as the new technology that will change organizations' strategies and operations. Perifanis and Kitsios (2023) also note that AI integration helps in decision support, reducing routine tasks and improving customer relationships. These technologies have benefits such as predictive analyses, resource utilization and operations. However, there are quite a few companies that have difficulty in effectively aligning AI with business models, which is a delicate process that requires management direction and resources.

Similarly, Keding (2021), agrees that AI has the potential to improve productivity and develop new revenue streams. It helps in segmenting markets, identifying customer churn and thus implementing appropriate marketing strategies to improve customer relationships. However, such implementation requires significant investment in various types of infrastructure as well as employee training.

Overall, the adoption of AI offers great opportunities for development and progress, but its effective utilization creates both opportunities and challenges that need to be purposefully managed.

3. Research methodology

As a part of this article, I have used a "secondary research approach" for the purpose of analyzing the effects of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on contemporary business. This kind of work is especially useful when there is no need for primary data collection because it provides a full picture of AI integration. And also the study integrates both "qualitative" and "quantitative" research methods:

Qualitative Research: This entails screening through of the available literature mainly articles from academic journals, industries reports and case analysis such as MDPI and Mckinsey respectively. It analyse how in the various businesses AI has been adopted and accomplished, also revealed strengths and weaknesses.

Quantitative Research: Research that involves credible sources such as IDEG, Gartner offer tangible figures including adoption and business revenue levels, productivity escalations, among others. These metrics corroborate the qualitative results and provide a quantitative approach to the results.

In this way, the study applies both logical and empirical research to provide a satisfactory overview of how AI influences the current enterprises' processes, both qualitatively and quantitatively.

4. Research Findings

The breakdown of the results obtained in this research is centered on corroborating the potential of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in today's business world. AI has enabled companies to innovate in multiple domains, creating tangible benefits and exposing challenges:

1. **Operational Advancements:** AI is extensively used in areas of managing task routines, the process of optimization and increasing efficiency. For instance, methods such as Robot and Artificial intelligence employs in industrial manufacturing have enhanced speed, and accuracy of the processes as compared to human work. Likewise, application of predictive maintenance with AI for industries such as aviation and automotive have reduced time and operation costs.

2. **Improved Decision-Making:** Due to the real time nature of analyses, the application of AI to process big data has had a significant impact on company decision-making. Today, demand forecasting, pricing methods, and risk assessment involve the use of AI in companies. Microsoft for example has had data analytics platforms backed by AI whereby salesforce has benefited from such platforms in the provision of insights that enhance performance.

3. **Customer Experience:** Digital techniques including artificial intelligence innovations for cases such as chatbot services, product or service recommendations, and analysis of customer sentiments all improve the customer experience. Netflix and Spotify rely on artificial intelligence to recommend the types of content clients are likely to enjoy most, a measure that helps increase their usage and loyalty levels.

4. **Emerging Opportunities:** AI helps develop innovative solutions by opening up new opportunities by creating new services and improving existing ones mostly in the field of healthcare, finances, and retail trade. For example, relative to diagnostics and fraud detection, the use of artificial intelligence avails precision and speed unlike in the past.

5. **Adoption Trends:** Reports from Gartner and McKinsey showed that there is still a need for improvement in the way organizations implement their AI systems in different industries especially that tech, finance and healthcare industries are at the front line. Still there are industries slowly venturing into utilizing AI such as agriculture and construction industries.

The presented information demonstrates that AI is both a powerful tool for generating more revenues and developing new products and services, as well as an object of various challenges in the sphere of its implementation. To make or achieve strategic use of AI efficiently depends on the good planning, infrastructure put in place, and an organizational culture that is receptive to change.

5. Discussion

The discussion focuses on the five sectors from the Research Findings: operational efficiency, decision-making, customer experience, emerging opportunities, and artificial intelligence adoption trends. These sectors are examples of how current companies are adjusting their operations to incorporate AI explaining both the strengths and the foregoing processes needed depending on the kind of AI device being integrated.

Operational Efficiency Over the years, organizations have incorporated AI as a main pillar of improving operation effectiveness in various sectors. Business solutions such as tactical technologies, intelligent operations, robotic process automation (RPA) and big data facilitate smooth operations and cut operational expenses. For instance, in supply chain, the utilization of AI to enhance the routes by which goods are delivered will reduce the time and cost incurred by organizations such as Amazon. Further, in the manufacturing sector, industries use artificial intelligence in checking product quality and ensure that all products produced meet exact quality standards through computer vision technology. According to Gartner, while giving more responsibility to people, the automation transfers between 20% and 30% of operational costs, which remains the primary reason for the rapid expansion of artificial intelligence throughout the world

Enhanced Decision-Making Through analyzing enormous datasets in real-time, AI has now become a new asset in making decisions. Algorithms are employed to make assumptions of the market, evaluate risks and make overall forecasts. Tesla, you saw, uses AI to make patterns of users in its products, therefore propelling its product marketing strategies. McKinsey indicates that organisations that link artificial intelligence to business strategies record an enhancement of their decision making by 20-40% than their competitors. AI also improves finance decision making and can carry out jobs such as the detection of fraud in banking and investment cases.

Customer Experience Such exceptional customer experience typical of AI has elevated the bar in customer relations and engagement. Products such as chatbots, recommendation engine, and sentiment analysis help the businesses to personalize the experiences. AI is used by Netflix and Spotify to suggest

the content, which matches the customers' behavior, ensuring increased customer engagement. If we use the strong argument: AI allows companies to deliver the 70% of global consumers, who expect personalization with brands. AI is also very important in real-time customer support and conversational agents addressing customer queries at any time maximizing convenience and speed.

Emerging Opportunities It plays an important role in creating innovations that help push technology into areas it has not really entered before. In healthcare, AI such as IBM Watson help doctors diagnose diseases with near precision, not forgetting that in agriculture machines learn algorithms to improve on yields by analyzing weather conditions and soil conditions. Companies in emerging markets especially in Asia-Pacific are quickly incorporating AI to quickly seek to leverage technologies that enable them to provide new services and improve efficiency. The use of AI in the retail Industry for instance; dynamic pricing which implies an automatic adjusting of the price of any material in line with the current demand.

AI Adoption Trends The adoption of Artificial Intelligence has increased tremendously with retail and financial organizations spearheading it. Gartner (2024) Impact Radar says that 60 percent of retail organisations already have at least one AI function in their operations, including predictive inventory management. Across the world, organizations that make investments in AI are benefiting and according to McKinsey, generative AI in isolation can provide up to \$ 4.4 trillion each year to corporate profits. Leading performers are not only acquiring technology, but also the complementing assets and trained people to leverage it.

6. Conclusion and Recommendation

I think it is clear now that Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a force multiplier for the contemporary business world, which paved the way for the reinvention of organizations and opening new horizons for various industries. As such it ensures optimality of operations thus affording companies the ability to minimize costs in operations and sustain unique competitive advantages. It clarify that information technology has advantages in handling big data and helping organizations make more informed decisions and this helps decision making in a firm to meet emerging markets needs and customer demands. Moreover, with the help of AI, customer relations became customized, so the bar for interaction was set higher comparing to the previously known forms of customer retention.

And also I'm sure that new ideas such as the use of AI in health care systems, in farming, and in the retail sector, this has uses from efficient diagnostics to real-time pricing strategy, which underscores the versatility of the use of the technology. However, for user organizations to be successful in adopting AI, there is a need to invest in infrastructure resources and talent and governance frameworks. Tapping into the potential of AI should be part of a consciously chosen company's development strategy in the context of the constantly progressing digital economy.

Nonetheless, the various opportunities present in adoption and use of AI have tradeoffs and some of them are pointed out below. Challenges like high costs, security of data and practicalities of decision making, that are potentially unethical, require coherent strategies and strategic planning. The speed at which AI is developing also requires that individuals and the organisations that employ them act fast in training its workforce and modifying organisational cultures to fully leverage the power of this transformative technology.

Recommendations

Strategic AI Integration: Companies should define which particular problems can be solved with the help of AI to create a relevant plan of action. Phase by phase approach helps users to effectively capture new aspects of change while at the same time excluding potential dangers that are associated with change.

Investment in Talent and Training: To adopt AI into their workplaces, organizations need to commit to hiring competent AI personnel and reintegrate their employees for new ways of working. Another important factor is to actually educate the employees about the AI concept and gain their attention to the new methods of collaboration.

Governance and Ethical Practices: Other risks, including data misuse and of algorithms are potential risks that should be overcome by developing a good governance structure. They also use client data for machine learning correctly to eliminate excessive or deviant reliance on algorithms in decision making processes.

Continuous Evaluation and Adaptation: AI technologies are not stagnant due to changes in the existing technology. AI plans in any organization should be periodically checked, mostly in terms of return on investment and uptake of new affinities to compete with other businesses.

I am quite sure that by implementing the given recommendations, companies will get the maximal benefit from AI and can freely adapt to the market changes to continue constant growth and increase the level of customers' satisfaction.

Reference List

1. Cam, A., Chui, M. and Hall, B. (2019). *Survey: AI Adoption Proves Its worth, but Few Scale Impact | McKinsey*. [Online] www.mckinsey.com. Available at: <https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/artificial-intelligence/global-ai-survey-ai-proves-its-worth-but-few-scale-impact> [Accessed 3 Dec. 2024].
2. Chui, M. and Yee, L. (2023). *AI Could Increase Corporate Profits by \$4.4 Trillion a year, According to New Research | McKinsey*. [Online] www.mckinsey.com. Available at: <https://www.mckinsey.com/mgi/overview/in-the-news/ai-could-increase-corporate-profits-by-4-trillion-a-year-according-to-new-research> [Accessed 3 Dec. 2024].
3. Gartner (2024). *Gartner: Fueling the Future of Business*. [online] Gartner. Available at: <https://www.gartner.com/en> [Accessed 2 Dec. 2024].
4. McKinsey (2022). *McKinsey & Company*. [online] McKinsey & Company. Available at: <https://www.mckinsey.com/> [Accessed 3 Dec. 2024].
5. Perifanis, N.-A. and Kitsios, F. (2023). Investigating the Influence of Artificial Intelligence on Business Value in the Digital Era of strategy: a Literature Review. *Information*, [online] 14(2). doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/info14020085>.
6. Perri, L. (2024). *Understand and Exploit GenAI with Gartner's New Impact Radar*. [online] Gartner. Available at: <https://www.gartner.com/en/articles/understand-and-exploit-gen-ai-with-gartner-s-new-impact-radar> [Accessed 3 Dec. 2024].
7. Roth, E. and Yee, L. (2024). *What McKinsey Learned While Creating Its Generative AI Platform*. [online] McKinsey & Company. Available at: <https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/mckinsey-digital/our-insights/what-mckinsey-learned-while-creating-its-generative-ai-platform> [Accessed 2 Dec. 2024].